

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE N 2 – Title GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

MILESTONE M3.4.2:

Availability of an innovative business model based on the BAT (Best Available Technologies) for the reconfiguration of production processes

DELIVERABLE D3.4.2:

Identification of an innovative business model for the reconfiguration of textile production processes

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M6 to M24
Periodic report date and version:	11/12/2024
Task 3.4.2 Responsible	Gianluigi Broggin, Elena Maggi
RM3 Responsible	Gianluigi Broggin

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Table - List of RM3 Project Milestones

Milestone No	Milestone Name	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Achieved	Comments
M 3.1.1	Availability of database (with digital toxicology analysis) and report of identified chemicals or polymers		Uniform resource locator or digital object identifier	M10 31/10/2023		18/10/2023	YES	File pdf in GRIP folder (30/11/2023)
M 3.1.2	Knowledge of the interests of industrial and logistics companies to design a reverse logistics		Based on the response of interest from industries	M10 31/10/2023	04/10/2024		NO	
M 3.4.1	Identification of products with potential industrial applications arising from enzymatic process		Letter of interest by industries	22				
M 3.4.2	Availability of an innovative business model based on the BAT (Best Available Technologies) for the reconfiguration of production processes		Uniform resource locator	24		11/12/2024	YES	File pdf in GRIP folder
M 3.5.1	Planning of related reverse logistics processes based on the use of more environmental friendly materials	3	Based on the response of interest from industries	24				
M 3.5.2	Identification and quantification of the micropollutants in surface water		Letter of interest by industries	26				

Table - List of RM3 Project Deliverables

D. No	Name	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Status	Comments
[number]	[name]	[R — Document, report] [DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA — data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP — Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]	[PU — Public] [SEN — Sensitive] [R] [C] [S]	[month number]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[Pending] [Draft] [Submitted] ([Rejected] [Approved] [Removed])	[insert comments]
D 3.4.1	Use of materials produced from enzymatic process to develop almost one sustainable alternative to current industrial processes	Other (Material)	PU	M 26			[Pending]	
D 3.4.2	Identification of an innovative business model for the reconfiguration of textile production processes	Other (Material)	PU	M 26		11/12/2024	[Pending]	
D 3.5.1	New products (Additives, auxiliary and finishing substances, dyes) for a textile supply chain	R/Other (Material)	PU	M 30			[Pending]	
D 3.5.2	Delineation of a ranking of chemicals or polymers (in case of microplastics) to be used with the local textile and chemical industries	Other (Material)	PU	M 32 AGOSTO 2025			[Pending]	

Request

Availability of an innovative business model based on the BAT (Best Available Technologies) for the reconfiguration of production processes.

Output

Currently, according to best available technology (BAT), grafting of vinyl monomers onto silk is accomplished using methacrylamide and a radical initiator, usually ammonium or potassium persulfate. This represents the only method adopted at the industrial level.

We have developed an innovative new approach that employs an alternative monomer and catalyst that provides the same industrial performance as the traditional method, but with significant improvements in environmental sustainability.

The product used meets the environmental certification standards found in the textile industry.

The process has been formalized and protected through the filing of a patent.

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU with grant agreement no. ECS00000036